

Socialism, Secularism and the Unstable Signposts of the Indian Democracy and Politics

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Abstract: It was needed to define democracy, socialism, and secularism in a pure scientific terms. Due to lack of proper definition and adequate propagation democracy has become synonymous to vote politics, socialism has been taken over by dynastic politics, castes, and secularism has taken over by religious fundamentalism. Therefore, mostly democracy, socialism, and secularism in India have remained in a para or sub state that created more and more problems. They never remained full, complete or, comprehensive. It was mainly due to failures of governmental or state institutions which never functioned scientifically and adjusted to suit individual and political preferences.

Key words: *Indian State; Democracy; Socialism, and Secularism.*

Introduction:

Democracy does not mean elections held every five years and then elected majority forming a government and taking decisions without the consent of the people. Likewise, socialism does not mean dynastic and caste politics or any kind of socialization of the politics. Socialism means social equality, control, and equaled distribution of income, resources, and opportunities. In addition, secularism does not mean a politics of appeasement and getting against or favoring a particular religion or politics.

India has been a classic example of taking great and doing something absolutely silly. The great ideas and notions like democracy, socialism, and secularism have been replaced by a politics of the dynasty, castes, and religion. Whereas, a government after getting elected do not consult people on vital issues and take decisions without their consent. This is not the ideas of democracy. A state has no moral right to impose its will over to a society and community. A state and a government should act and behave in a manner that do not violate the respective social objectives and efforts of different social groups until and unless they came in conflict with other social groups. More and more powers should be given to the communities. People remained choice less and selected one political formation or other.

The core foundation on which this whole concept of Indian state bases upon such as socialism, secularism, and democracy has been diluted and compromised. Democracy has compromised with dynasty politics, secularism compromised by appeasement politics or fundamentalism, and ultimately socialism compromising with dynasty and caste politics. Socialist leaders have adopted caste and categories politics as their main weapon. Ultimately, all those resulted in Hinduism becoming synonymous to *Brahmanism* and Secularism also getting restricted to safeguarding the interests of *Brahmanism*. In any case, both Hinduism and secularism were initially propagated and patronized by Brahmins. However, things changed because of Brahmins getting replaced from the top positions in political parties and democratic institutions.

The organized dogmatism and skepticism spread by the media failed to lure the population and all new political forms developed in the country excluding Brahmins. In this new formation backward castes, dalits, and minorities came

together. However, several such new formations faced corruption charges and criticized for supporting a dynasty politics.

India stood at the brink of a very important historic moment with the culmination of 16th Lok Sabha elections. One of the most important issues flagged by the numerous debates on the issue of elections was what these elections meant for the state of Indian secularism. This issue was highlighted even more as the fear of Hindu-right wing political forces coming to power grew in the minds of the secular ranks of society. However, it is also a truth that this new government did not represent a united Hindu mandate because the Prime Ministers proclamation that he belonged to a poor backward caste has irked 22 percent upper caste population. This state has not been digested by upper caste, however, they would not have minded in *Narendra Modi* terming him as a son of Tea Seller. Brahmins trying to remain in the corridors of power ultimately making way and supporting a backward prime minister thinking they would safeguard their interests. However, a leader of the country, especially a prime minister should keep away from the politics of backward and forward.

The Indian state and the ruling elite committed to the capitalist modernization have failed in propagating the ideology of secularism and in shaking off the shackles of religion, caste and community loyalties which are binding on all classes in India. The modern India state has to grapple with the challenges posed by communal forces. Therefore, we must oppose communalism, not only in the minority but also in the majority if we do not want to weaken the growth of real democracy and secular spirit. The real challenge to modern India state is from organized religious groups. The internal weakness of the Indian state is and will be exploited by the imperialists who have important stakes in our country which is following the path of capitalist modernization and globalization. This is a real threat to the National Integration of India to sum up the political scene in India is intricate and the equation between secularism and communal politics covers only a small part of the picture. Any state is inherently a secular power, although it may not always be secular minded. The definition of secularism as the divorce in the state from religion or from the churches is derived from the history of the emergence of the modern European states in struggles against church dominance. A more general definition of secularism is the determination of a people to uphold a self-governing

political community. This involves the acceptance of self-responsibility of the citizens. The prevalence of tolerant policies and attitudes is the need of the hour. During the last 56 years of India's independence, India has witnessed both successes and failures in running the secular democratic processes. It has evolved a lasting secular constitution, a viable political system and a functional federal secular polity and with strong democratic traditions. Diverse races and ethnic-lingual groups have been unified without destroying their identities. Above all, a vast multi-religious, multi-ethnic and multi-cultural India has been kept united. These achievements, however, are facing serious challenges from the negative trends that have crept in over the years. Communal, caste and linguistic tensions are growing in such proportion that the unity of India appears to be threatened. The use of violence in communal and caste politics has given legitimacy to communal violence and crime in politics. The former election commissioner G.V.G Krishna Murthy, has gone on record to say that the situation in India is threatening to degenerate into a "government of the criminals, for the criminals and by the criminals. Such a sorry state of affairs cannot be allowed to continue for long periods. The doctrines of liberty, equality, Fraternity, social justice, secularism, fair play and the rule of law enshrined in the Indian constitution have to percolate into our daily lives. The government, the political parties, and Indian citizens all must play their effective role in the fight against these challenges, particularly the challenge of communalism. There is no doubt that with the efforts of younger generation India can look forward to emerging as a great secular nation (Hussain, 2015).

India is slowly moving away from secularism because secularism is not digested well by some groups. Nevertheless, such groups Dr. Radhakshnan writes "we should not confuse secularism with the concept of atheism because the type of secularism, we are trying to achieve is very much in consonance with the old religious ideals as Smith has noted "Most of Hindu legislations regard temple entry laws as measures of social reform motivated by humanitarian considerations and concern for social justice. They fail to appreciate the predominant religious aspect in this area of reform".

Donald Smith defines a secular state as one which guarantees individual and corporate freedom of religion, deals with individual as citizen irrespective of religion nor does it seek to promote or interfere with religion. This has been incorporated in the Indian Constitution. However, Luther contends that the Indian State is not secular since it does not clearly demarcate between the State and the Church in the manner in which, for example, the United States of America does (Mondal, 2015).

Another charge put forth by Lutheran and also endorsed by Smith is that the Indian State, in spite of the constitutional guarantee of liberty of the individual and the liberty of corporate religious bodies, intervenes in religious matters.

This has been described as inconsistency in the growth of secularism in India. He writes, despite claims made for religious neutrality the State of India has often intervened in the religious matters; this particularly holds in the case of management of temples and religious institutions, such as monasteries and monastic heads.

There is no doubt that some provisions of the Constitution and some of the laws passed do interfere with the religious customs and practices of Hindus. The religious tolerance or non-intervention does not mean secularism. Rather partial non-intervention has led to religious fundamentalism in place of growth of humanism. The conflict on Ramjanambhumi and Babri Mosque is the bright example of fundamentalism. Thus, religious fundamentalism has been indicative of a 'breakdown'

of the secularization process in India. It has brought an escalation of ethno-religious conflicts and national disintegration.

Critics have alleged that the Indian polity has not been able to develop along true secular lines and it suffers from serious shortcomings. Some of the important factors which have impeded the growth of normal secularism in India are as follows:

A problem of uniform civil code is essential in the direction of bringing about national identity and the integration of members of all religious communities into one bond of common citizenship. Following independence, it was hoped that this step would be taken to usher in secular society. But unfortunately till now no progress has been made in the evolution of a uniform Civil Code and today its adoption appears to be more problematic than it was at the time when the Constitution was framed.

Thus, the Muslim minority compelled the Government, in 1986, to enact legislation concerning maintenance of divorced women, which it felt was closer to its Personal Law and, therefore, religiously more acceptable. Modern secular considerations, and the opinion of those Muslims who took a secular position, were given no cognizance by the Government.

Similarly, other minorities like Christians and Sikhs, too, have given some indications that would render the formulation and enforcement of a uniform Civil Code an impossibility. Such limitations indicate that the path leading to a truly secular society in India is strewn with numerous hurdles.

The political parties in India have tended to use religion and caste factors for the promotion of their political interests and thus greatly undermined the secular values.

The growing communalism also greatly hampered the growth of genuine secularism in India. Despite the abandonment of communal electorates and a ban on the use of religion for soliciting votes, the various political parties and groups have frequently made use of communal factors to get into power. In this regard both the minorities as well as the majority communities are equally to blame. Unless this feeling of communalism is shunned, secularism cannot take firm roots in the Indian soil.

The responsibility of undermining India's limited secularism falls upon the shoulders of the leaders of the post-Nehru era, many of whom are not intellectually liberated, because of their traditional background, to understand arid to appreciate genuine secularism. Due to their neo-traditional orientation, these leaders is lacking in true commitment to the secularization of Indian society, not only in terms of developing non-religious outlook but also in terms of developing a rational and scientific temper. This failure of the leadership has thwarted the progressive separation of religion and politics in India.

The failure of the government to evolve a just economic order and eliminate poverty also gave a serious setback to secularism. The common masses suffering from deprivation and grinding poverty could not develop any faith in the polity which failed to provide them basic necessities and consequently did not attach much importance to secular values.

Many public rituals and ceremonials like Bhoomi puja, breaking of coconuts on inaugural or auspicious occasions, performing of 'Aarti' and applying to 'Tilak' to distinguished guests are perceived by Hindus as cultural or nationalistic expressions, but to non-Hindus these are manifestations of Hindu culture. Such rituals are performed even on state functions and therefore, create unnecessary misgivings about the neutrality of the State.

The confusion between "Hindu" and "Indian" has largely arisen in the last forty years. The cultural dimension of secularism has been totally neglected, and we have, therefore, neither attempted to develop a composite Indian culture based on a true amalgam of all religious sub-cultures, nor have we developed a new culture based on secular values, with emphasis on secular symbols. Of course, this was not an easy task, but efforts to have been lacking.

Of late an attempt has been made by a sizeable section of the Indian society to equate Hindu cultural symbols as a national culture. This is possibly the expression of what has been called the "Hindu backlash", which is believed to be the consequence of rise in Muslim and Hindu fundamentalism. But this, or any other, explanation does not condone the lapses of the State in this regard. Such insensitivity to the feelings of the minorities destroys the credibility of the secular professions of the State.

Due to the limited interpretation of secularism, as being confined to State policy only, the religious identities and other sub-cultural differences of Indian citizens have continued to remain strong. In societies where such distinctions are emphasized, groups and communities remain distanced from one another.

Apart from education and jobs, prejudice and discrimination are perceived as operating in the matter of intergroup violence and conflict. There is now ample evidence to show that at times the administrative machinery of the State does not operate impartially at the time of communal riots; those responsible for ensuring law and order act in a non-secular way and tend to victimize members of minority groups.

The minorities are in fear of the giant majority, which has the brute strength to overpower them and divests them of their distinctive characteristics. Furthermore, loyalties continue to be particularistic rather than universalistic.

The defective educational system which has encouraged the people to think in terms of groups and communities, has also failed to inculcate secular ideas in the minds of young students and promote a feeling of mutual give and take.

The distortion of the Constitution and democratic institutions has also greatly contributed to the weakening of the secularism in India. The Constitution and the political institutions have not worked the way they were envisaged by the framers of the Constitution. For example, though use of religion is not permitted for soliciting votes, yet certain religious, political parties have made free use of factors like religion, caste etc. to secure votes. All this has hampered the growth of a true secular polity in the country

The number of sons, daughters, wives and other relatives that politicians come attached with reminds me of Bollywood. Talent takes a back seat, and nepotism rules. Whether it is the Gandhis, or the Scandia's or the Karunanidhis, India is fast becoming a shining example of dynastic politics. But then political dynasties are perpetuated because voters vote them in, and then the party members elevate them to great heights

Dynasty is a tenacious glue that holds political parties together, whether it is the Congress or regional behemoths. But it is not enough in a democracy (Tully, 2012).

Mark Tully Further says in his article, Feudalism is a definition of medieval European society, and many historians question whether it is even a useful concept for describing those times. Yet the word feudal is loosely bandied about to deplore today's dynastic democracy in India. Coming a little nearer to our time, it's also often suggested that India's dynasties show that democracy here is stuck in the rut that constrained British politics some 300 years ago, the days of rotten boroughs, boroughs so small that each voter could be personally bribed. I

would suggest that India's democratic dynasties have arisen because they suit the circumstances prevailing today. They are modern political hybrids.

There is no doubt that dynasties abound in India. The most obvious example is the Nehru-Gandhi dynasty, which dominates the Congress party. Indira Gandhi is usually credited with converting Congress into a family business, but in his recently published autobiography, Kuldip Nayar says Lal Bahadur Shastri believed Nehru had dynastic ambitions, wanting his daughter to succeed him. In the regions, there are powerful dynastic patriarchs, for instance, Mulayam Singh in the north, M. Karunanidhi in the south, and Naveen Patnaik in the east. It has recently been estimated that a little over 28 per cent of the current MPs are dynasts. However, Indian politicians seem to need a strong leader to keep them in order. Congress is suffering because Indira Gandhi laid down the rule that no politician should be allowed to become a regional Dynast.

Dynasty politics is not an India specific problem as it also very much existed in the entire sub-continent and even in developed country's democracy. Before condemning India's dynastic politics with pejorative terms like feudal, and backward, it should be remembered that doughnuts are a widespread phenomenon in Asia. Singapore, whose economic progress is so widely praised, is effectively run by the Lee family. The much admired Burmese opposition leader Aung San Suu Kyi is the daughter of the independence hero Aung San. In neighboring Bangladesh, two formidable women dynasts battle for power: Hasina Wajed, daughter of Sheikh Mujib, the leader of the independence movement, and Khaleda Zia, widow of the assassinated military ruler Ziaur Rahman. One of the many questions hanging over the future of Pakistan is whether Benazir Bhutto's son Bilawal will be able to safeguard the dynasty founded by Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto. Even in China, sons and daughters of leading party members have become known as 'red princes' because of the influence they wield. With the Roosevelts, the Kennedys, and of course, the Bush family, America can't afford to sneer at Indian dynasts. Britain just witnessed the most amazing outpouring of affection on Queen Elizabeth's diamond jubilee, and she is a dynasty if ever there was one.

Mark R. Thompson, a professor at the University of Hong Kong, has written an article on Asian dynasties in which he argues that they are not throwbacks to 'age-old ways'. He says dynasticism works in modern political systems because "it appeals to notions of inherited charisma that help legitimize leadership succession and minimize organizational division".

In India, dynasts do seem able to hold parties together. I remember suggesting to a senior Congressman that the party might ditch Rajiv Gandhi when his fortunes were at their lowest. The Congressman was shocked, "The Nehru-Gandhi family is the keystone of the party," he said. "Take them out and the party collapses." Subsequent events were to prove him right. The Congress did come very near to collapsing after Ayodhya, when that wily politician Arjun Singh mounted his campaign against Prime Minister P.V. Narasimha Rao. Mind you, the apparently reluctant Dynast Sonia Gandhi played a role in undermining Narasimha Rao's authority from behind the purdah. Who's to know where Congress would have been today if Sonia hadn't eventually decided to pull off a coup and take control of the family party?

Indian politicians seem to need a strong leader to keep them in order. There must be many in the BJP who, seeing the disarray in their leaderless party, wish Atal Bihari Vajpayee had an heir. Congress is suffering because Indira Gandhi laid down the rule that no Congress politician should be allowed to become a regional Dynast, powerful enough to challenge the likes of a

Karunanidhi. In this year's Uttar Pradesh Assembly elections, lack of a regional dynasty left the Congress entirely dependent on Rahul Gandhi's charisma to combat the two deeply entrenched dynasts, Mulayam and Mayawati. Mayawati is a dynasty because the founder of her party, Kanshi Ram, bequeathed the leadership to her.

Dynastic democracy has wrought a revolution in caste by empowering those who were traditionally powerless. But it's India's family traditions that justify dynasts in the eyes of voters. Does Rahul Gandhi's failure to pull off a miracle in Uttar Pradesh mean that he has no magic, no dynastic charisma? The crowds that turned out for him argue the opposite. But what those lazy Congress politicians who routinely rely on the charisma of the Nehru-Gandhi dynasty to win elections since they forget is that charisma alone is rarely enough to win votes and crowds are not a reliable indication of voters' intentions. Travelling with Rajiv Gandhi from Jhansi to Kanpur during his 1991 election campaign, the vast, enthusiastic crowds who mobbed him might well have swept me off my feet. I could well have believed that he had the election in the bag. But the results indicated that without the tragedy of his assassination, Congress may well not have formed the next government and even with the sympathy vote, it didn't win an absolute majority.

Caste cements most regional dynasties and both Congress and BJP do their caste calculations. Although this is almost universally condemned, dynastic democracy has wrought a revolution in caste by empowering those who were traditionally powerless. But it's India's strong family traditions, so different to the nuclear families in the West that justify dynasts in the eyes of voters. In India, it's widely thought to be natural and acceptable for a father or a mother who has any form of power to want to hand it over to a son or a daughter. Inder Malhotra has put it very well. In his book *Dynasties of India and beyond*, he said "the vocal minority's denunciation of dynasties-particularly loud in India and primarily directed against the Nehru-Gandhi's-is indeed out of sync with the basic reflex of the silent majority... To the bulk of the subcontinent's population, there seems nothing objectionable in political power passing from parent to progeny".

Inder does describe the silent majority as "retarded socially". That seems to me derogatory, a description which could be taken to imply that Indian democracy is feudal and backward. I prefer to see dynasties as serving the needs of the present times in India, preserving democracy by providing a measure of stability. Looking to the future, I hope that dynasties will become less important, but that doesn't mean India should slavishly follow the path of western democracy. After all, America, which shouts loudest about democracy, could be described as a plutocracy, such is the wealth required to enter the political fray as a major player there.

The phenomenon spans the map of India Karunanidhi's DMK in the South, Mulayam Singh Yadav's SP in the North, BAL Thackeray's Shiv Sena in the West and Naveen Patnaik's BJD in the East. Lalu Yadav in Bihar, Farooq Abdullah and Mufti Mohammad in Kashmir also infected with the dynasty virus. Widespread public acceptance is the most important one since people relate to the individual more than the party that the candidate represents. This is true because in the majority of the cases, the movement of the person across parties also translates into the movement of votes for the party. Indians possess an unending fascination with the members of the Gandhi family right from the days of Jawaharlal Nehru. One more compelling reason is that after having established a stronghold (and a brand), why not capitalize and provide a ready field to the next Gen guys and continue the legacy?

Politics is perhaps the only field where you can enjoy the largest of returns with the smallest of investments. According to some sociologists the argument about dynasty politics is irrelevant in a country like ours since out here, inheritance is a birthright.

And like umpteen other things, if you thought that "it happens only in India" then you probably have got it wrong. Uncle Sam did it with the Kennedys, Dubya, Al Gore et al; Pakistan did it with Benazir Bhutto (due to her father, Zulfikar Ali Bhutto) and now Mr. Asif Ali Zardari; Sri Lanka did it with Chandrika Kumaratunge; Bangladesh did it with Sheikh Hasina; North Korea, Iraq and the list doesn't end.

Despite major strides in economic reform over the past 30 years, major aspects of the Indian economy retain a smothering level of government involvement. Narendra Modi's popularity suggests India could witness a permanent shift away from the pasta tectonic shift to the right in India's economic discourse. I doubt we are so lucky. Rather, the reflexive reach of socialist-style solutions is likely to prove a hard habit to kick.

No other term better captures the heavy state intervention existing in too many markets. Socialist policies include public sector undertakings and price controls. They include market micro-management for which the regulatory objective long ago ended, such as the Agricultural Produce Marketing Committee (APMC) Acts or setting targets for bank lending. These are state-run for the sake of keeping control with the state, when less controlling alternatives exist—hence the term socialism.

The details of Modi's economic agenda remain murky for the moment, but he has spoken out against socialist strategies. Lighten the regulatory burden, shrink the government footprint. I contend that three factors will help make this shift away from socialist economic policies a permanent one.

First, as recent financial market performance would imply, a pro-business style of government at the centre holds the potential to return India to the high growth trajectory of the last decade. Ideally, this will be done by facilitating manufacturing growth. Manufacturing produces better jobs and the sort of inclusive growth that benefit incumbents.

It will take time and hard work to make the business environment more inviting to manufacturing, but results should be visible within five years. Good results should help re-elect and continued centre-right economic policies.

Second, Modi has indicated a desire to tackle labour reform. Indeed, he will be hard-pressed to advance job creation without it. Trade unions and socialist policies have a symbiotic coexistence. Unions help block reforming labour regulation or reducing government holdings of public sector undertakings (PSUs). This protects union membership.

Accordingly, the decline of one often leads to decline in the other. This is a pattern seen in many countries having already undertaken such reforms. If Modi reforms labour markets, declining political power of trade unions in India will weaken the impulse towards socialist policies in the future.

Third, the most prominent proponents of socialism, the left-wing of the Congress Party, may never recover. The younger generation of Congress leaders is more likely to have an American MBA than student organizer credentials. If Congress regains relevance, it will not likely lean so far left.

Unfortunately, a permanent shift away from new socialist policies will not likely succeed in sweeping out the plentiful vestiges of socialism remaining in Indian government. Another three arguments can be made that their survival is secure.

First, there are limits even to Modi's power. Many other observers have cautioned that state governments hold the keys to many major reforms. Union labour ministry data shows, for example, that 40% of employees in public sector undertakings (PSUs) work for state-level PSUs.

Second, less government means reducing Modi's own authority. Any leader must maintain party discipline and entice the cooperation of outside groups. Having already reduced the number of cabinet seats, Modi will need to find other enticements for horse trading. He may need to be able to dole out the spoils of big government operations.

A year ago Modi advocated their privatization. Recently he has spoken only about revitalizing them. Even if his administration does reform them—which also means lowering their loyalty-generating value to whomever control is given—they remain a tempting target for future administrations.

Modi cannot stay forever. Better for India to privatize PSUs now, especially while markets are so hot. This removes the temptation to return PSUs to the sad, inefficient, politically driven state they are in today.

Third, socialism is often populism in disguise, and populism is still popular. Jayalithaa-style giveaways may be pure populism, but fuel subsidies, commodity trading bans and directed lending are not much better. They have the objective of protecting the poor, but we all know the middle class benefits more.

I can think of no faster path to unpopularity in India than removing energy subsidies, yet Modi cannot succeed in either reining in the fiscal deficit or improving power supply without drastically scaling them back. Modi may yet choose to risk popular hostility, but the reformist path is not a foregone conclusion.

Do not interpret this invective against socialism to imply the government should shrink in all dimensions. Programs tackling important problems in innovative ways deserve support. The Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme (MGNREGS), for instance, should be improved, not discarded. And of course India needs more government provision of public goods such as infrastructure, courts, police, healthcare and education.

Rather than less government, India needs a government restructuring. Shift away from unnecessary socialist meddling and focus on high performance in core areas. Modi's CEO-style of governance should give confidence in the latter (Green, 2015).

No matter what we may think about the actual experience of socialism in the past, one thing is undeniable. It was the first time in human history that a society had come into being not spontaneously, not on the basis of the spontaneous movement of history independent of human will, but on the basis of human conception. Karl Marx had remarked in *Capital* that the difference between the best bee and the worst architect is that the architect, unlike the bee, erects a structure in the mind before erecting it in reality. Socialism is the first structure of society that was first erected in the mind before it was erected in reality. True, what came into being might not have fully corresponded to what was in the mind; nonetheless socialism, even as it existed, was the first *non-spontaneously evolved mode of production in human history*. Quite apart from its historical significance in establishing the rule of the hitherto exploited classes, in defeating fascism, in enabling the oppressed nations to liberate themselves from imperialism and in forcing capitalism, however transiently, to adopt welfare state measures, this aspect of socialism, of representing the first grand effort of mankind to transform a vision into reality,

must never be lost sight of. In fact, socialism defined, to a significant extent, the contours of human civilization advance in the 20th century and left an ineradicable imprint on all its aspects. Since mankind would never again rest content leaving its fate to the blind forces of history, the victory of socialism, not necessarily *in the form it originally appeared in but may be in some other form, representing a vision going beyond capitalism towards social ownership, is assured and inevitable*. Through all our present travails this is a truth we must never lose sight of.

Nonetheless, we must face the question: why did socialism collapse over large parts of the world? The usual answer to this question focuses on the defects of the system that was erected, notably the extreme centralization of power in the socialist societies, which were characterized by a dictatorship of the Party and which ultimately ended up de-politicizing the working class to a significant extent. The CPI (M) had, in its 14th Congress, identified four areas viz, the character of the socialist State; the content of socialist democracy; the construction of the socialist economy; and inadequate development of ideological consciousness amongst the people, where distortions and deviations took place undermining the socialist State. There is of course much truth in this. *But this answer itself has to be located within a historical context*, and that context was provided by imperialism. Imperialism leading to uneven development kept socialism confined only to countries in the periphery while countries in the metropolis, belying the hopeful anticipation of Marx and Engels and the expectations of Lenin and his comrades, came close to, but never succeeded in, achieving the breakthrough to a socialist revolution. As a result, socialism, wherever it had come into being, remained "encircled" throughout its entire brief history, resulting in an ossification of the centralized bureaucratic structure from which there was no escape other than through a collapse of the system itself.

There is an additional point to note. Not only did revolutions not happen in the advanced centres of capitalism, but the very revolutionary conjuncture it passed. The Program of the Cominter was based on the notion of a "general crisis of capitalism" from which the only way out could be provided with a transition to socialism. All of us recollect the meetings of 1957 and 1960. 81 Communist parties in a declaration asserted in 1960 that the international correlation of forces shifted *decisively* in socialism's favor; that capitalism is incapable of developing any further; that socialism is irreversible in the existing socialist countries, etc. etc. In retrospect, it is clear that there was both an underestimation of capitalism and an overestimation of socialism. An incorrect estimation that had grave consequences for the advance of the socialist cause. Capitalism restructured itself in the aftermath of the Second World War, through Keynesian demand management ushering in an unprecedented boom, through political de-colonization removing the moral stigma of being an oppressor of other nations from it, and through the diffusion of a degree of development to certain pockets in the third world, such as East Asia, which appeared to belie the Sixth Congress thesis that the development of the third world could occur only through socialism. These changes together with the experience of the very horrors of the Second World War contributed to the passing of the revolutionary conjuncture of the period 1913-1950. While we have a renascent imperialism today and the moral stigma associated with oppression and stagnation is once again beginning to adhere to capitalism, portending the beginning of yet another possible revolutionary conjuncture, the fact remains that this would not be a return to the earlier conjuncture. Lenin always teaches us that concrete analysis of concrete conditions is the living essence of dialectics. Just as he authored Leninism as Marxism in the era of imperialism, it falls on our collective shoulders to define the

contours of the socialist revolution in the present conjecture. *Therefore, there is no going back. We can stand on Lenin's shoulders to see the future, but we cannot see it through Lenin's eyes.*

Given the fact of uneven development under imperialism, it is clear that the transition to socialism would be a protracted affair. Likewise, given the reassertion of hegemony of imperialism in the epoch of the emergence of a new form of international finance capital, it is clear that the socialist movement must be engaged above all in an anti-imperialist struggle. Indeed the chief hallmark of the socialist movement today is that it constitutes the most consistent fighter against imperialism, since it alone can visualize a transcendence of capitalism which is a necessary condition for the transcendence of imperialism. For, Marx has irrefutably proved that capitalism can never survive without its *raison-d-etre*, i.e., the exploitation of man by man and nation by nation. To those who spread illusions of reforming capitalism (since Bernstein) and to those who parrot the TINA (there is no alternative to globalization) factor, the Communist answer can only be that the alternative to TINA is SITA -- socialism is the alternative. We can therefore carry the struggle for socialism forward today only through the adoption of an uncompromising stand against imperialism. This is our historic task in an era when the vileness of imperialist predetermines, notwithstanding all high phrases about "freedom" and "democracy", is becoming apparent to everyone in the aftermath of the war in Iraq.

There is an additional point to consider. The reassertion of imperialist hegemony is occurring in a situation of the ascendancy of international finance capital in a new form *which has the effect of causing deflation, recession, and unemployment everywhere*. In other words, the contemporary imperialist aggressiveness is the other side of the same coin which imposes enormous burdens on the working classes in the advanced capitalist countries in the form of unemployment and cuts in social wage. Imperialism of course tries to pit the workers in the advanced countries against those in the third world by arguing that the latter are snatching jobs away from the former. Nothing could be further from the truth. It is the world-wide deflation imposed by finance capital that is the cause of unemployment everywhere, not the re-distribution of employment from one section of workers from another. An anti-imperialist struggle, provided it can make this point clear and present a vision for improving the lot of mankind as a whole, embracing the working class and other exploited classes in *all* countries -- developed, developing and underdeveloped - - can acquire world-wide support and contribute to a change in the conjuncture.

Of course the precise contours of what a future socialist society would look like still need to be drawn, based on the past experience of socialism. The road map of this would naturally vary from country to country depending on the concrete realities. Each one of us has this historic responsibility to discharge in our respective countries. However, the task of advancing the anti-imperialist struggle worldwide cannot afford to wait. Neither can it wait until that intellectual task of evolving a coherent nor is the comprehensive revolutionary theory of the socialist revolution in the present conjecture, important though it is, completed.

Finally, let us confront a reality squarely. The present phase of capitalist globalization is simply unsustainable. This is precisely because, by sharply accentuating economic inequalities -- between countries and between the rich and poor in individual countries -- the vast majority of the world's population is increasingly placed beyond market operations as they simply lack the requisite purchasing power. Imperialist hegemonic drive, therefore, will increasingly be determined by military aggressiveness. Under these conditions,

as Rosa Luxembourg said earlier and as Fidel Castro says today, the choice before humanity's future is between socialism and barbarism.

Each one of us, working in tandem with our domestic revolutionary goals, will have to work for integrating the worldwide anti-globalization protests with the global anti-war upsurge into a mighty anti-imperialist movement. This requires, simultaneously, the intensification of the ideological combat within these movements that seek to obfuscate socialism as the only alternative available to humanity (Yechury, 2004).

India is poised for her next historic tryst with destiny. The 21st century means new hopes and fresh aspirations amongst people everywhere. For India, the 20th century was of momentous significance. We took giant strides that released the people and the country from the shackles of colonialism, which had not only squeezed the wealth of India but also fettered our freedom. The spirit of India, the genius of her people, we thought, had been released from subjugation and exploitation and we had assumed control over our destiny.

The promise and commitment that India did to her people over 65 years ago remain unfulfilled and there are incomplete and urgent tasks that we have to finish soon. To identify the challenges of the next millennium, India will have to clear the huge backlog of unredeemed promises. She has to fight hunger, poverty and unemployment and cater to such needs of the people as education, health, potable drinking water, housing and rural electrification. The farmer has to be able to use his land and labour to not merely sustain himself and his family, but to earn the wealth that lies in his land. The working class, especially labour in the factories, should be able to share the prosperity that is now confined to a very thin layer of the population. India will have to meet the challenges of liberating and empowering women, as the country has to release the backward and the exploited from the age-old bonds of caste and conflicts.

In history, the 20th century will be recorded as a century marked by contradictions. Periods of optimism and hope were followed by despair and despondency. The past hundred years saw tremendous advances in science and technology and witnessed two global wars which caused the sufferings of unprecedented proportions to humanity the century welcomed the triumph of liberation struggles in Asia, Africa and Latin America vitiating the process of de-colonization. We saw the end of social apartheid in South Africa and the awakening of progressive forces demanding the establishment of a democratic order based on the primacy of human values and socioeconomic justice. We experienced the establishment of socialist governments and the creation of a socialist bloc, which at one point encompassed one-fifth of the world population. This tide that had swept through the world radiating outwards from the Soviet Union to China, Vietnam and far away Cuba seemed to recede. Rampant capitalism in the garb of essential economic structural re-engineering took over and plunged the Russian Republic into chaos. From the high point of hope, we witnessed the decline and the break-up of the Soviet Union and the socialist forces in the world received a major setback. Fortunately, there still exist some socialist countries, including China, the most populous country in the world. India has to closely follow their policies and development and draw appropriate lessons. There is hope that disquieting trends will be reversed and a new situation will emerge in the next century.

The 20th century has been the story of a dialectical ebb and flow in the tide of human progress. Much of what we are expected to experience in the next millennium would be shaped by the developments of our century. The same

paradigm is applicable to India, too. Any discourse on political leadership in contemporary India should focus on the role and contribution of Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru. Along with Mahatma Gandhi, Vallabhbhai Patel, Subhas Chandra Bose and many others, he played a major role in the shaping of modern India. It is, perhaps, appropriate that would touch on some of his contributions at this address organized by the trustees of the Jawaharlal Nehru Memorial Fund.

Nehru occupies a significant place in our history. Between 1947 and 1964, he, as the first Prime Minister of independent India, guided her destiny. Throughout the nationalist struggle, Nehru symbolized the left and secular forces within the Indian National Congress. His presidential address at the 1936 session, especially, inspired this country's youth. What singled him out was his intellectual ability to combine his commitment to the cause of national liberation with other progressive forces in world politics. His visit to the USSR in 1927 gave him a firsthand experience that he cherished. Pandit Nehru condemned, in no uncertain terms, the invasion of China by Japan and took prompt steps to send a medical team to China as a mark of solidarity. He was one of the staunchest critics of fascism and went to Spain to boost the morale of the Republicans fighting the Spanish Civil War. Nehru also unequivocally disapproved of the Munich Pact of 1938. His vision of India's role in the international order gave birth to the non-aligned movement, which has been a major contribution to the structuring of international affairs in the post-colonial period.

Pandit Nehru visited England twice and on both occasions, the London Majlis organized receptions in his honor. While Vijay Lakshmi Pandit was with him during the first visit, Indira accompanied him

Impressed by the erstwhile Soviet Union's achievements through five-year plans, Pandit Nehru adopted centralized planning as the best strategy for India's economic and social development and initiated the process of industrialization. He was an ardent believer in the development of India based on democracy and secularism. As a founding father of non-alignment, he made the country a force to reckon with in international politics. India began her career with much promise, but half a century after independence much of what Jawaharlal Nehru had visualized has been belied.

Nehru wanted to put into practice his concept of 'mixed economy' with a view to reducing social and economic distress. In reality, the feudal-capitalistic system continues. Even here, much could have been done if the political will to change has been stronger. But the general scenario today is far from satisfactory. Without land reforms and democratic decentralization, there persists a high degree of concentration of wealth and power in the hands of the few. An unwieldy bureaucracy has flourished, while the vast masses are steeped in poverty. Distortions in the functioning of the Constitution have led to inequalities in economic advance, a centralized political structure and regional disparities, which, at times, trigger centrifugal outbursts.

The Indian polity betrays disturbing signs of political centralism. The centrist and authoritarian tendencies of the central government reached its peak during the emergency in 1975 when the people of India were deprived of the fundamental rights that are enshrined in the country's Constitution. Indian federalism, with its strong centralizing tendencies, allowed on many occasions the ruling parties in Delhi to not only intervene, but also destabilize state governments, which were of a different political hue. India's democratic tradition re-asserted itself by rejecting authoritarianism and the emergency ended in two years. Mrs. Gandhi later why she had taken such an undemocratic and

extreme step. Her answer was that the country was going to pieces and the people were in no mood to listen to the advice of the government. She thought that a shock therapy was necessary to bring back the people on the right track. However, they registered their strong protest when the opportunity came. The Congress as a ruling party enjoyed a virtual monopoly of power for 46 years. Unfortunately, it failed to combat the politics of religious sectarianism and fundamentalism.

The need to look at things afresh and to reorient ourselves for the next century is becoming increasingly urgent. The restructuring of Centre-State relations on a healthy note has been hanging fire for a long time. The Sarkaria Commission has not helped to resolve this issue. It is of the view that the nation can be made powerful by making only the centre more powerful. The Commission has recommended, by and large, status quo in the Centre-State relations, especially in the areas, relating to legislative matters, role of Governors, use of Article 356etc. My differences on major aspects of the Sarkaria Commission's report have been made known to all. Article 6 was misused in the past by different central governments to serve their partisan purposes. Both Article 356 and 357 need to be amended to preclude further possibilities of such misuse. It is, however, necessary to mention that even those recommendations of the Sarkaria commission that have gone in favor of the states are yet to be implemented.

In order to build a strong centre, the country needs strong states. There is an urgent necessity for transferring far more powers from the centre to the states and only fundamental realignment can form the basis of a strong nation. If necessary, this should be brought about by enacting further constitutional amendments. Creating smaller states as proof of federalist commitment is not the answer. This is a political weapon that the BJP is using to create constituencies for itself. By this, it will further encourage disunity and conflict in the country and help reactionary forces. What is required is to adopt the policy of granting greater autonomy within the state wherever necessary. The faltering development of a full-fledged civil society in India has undermined the working of political democracy in the country. Creation of castes and religious vote-banks, use of money, corruption in high places, muscle-power and the criminal-political nexus is only some of our social-political ills. The events since the eighties have been causing serious concern to all right-thinking forces.

The despicable act of the demolition of the Babri Masjid in 1992 perpetrated by the fundamentalists, and its communal fall-out tarnished the image of India. The BJP-led Government proclaimed in its National Agenda that it would uphold what it called real secularism, which is in reality a call for changing the accepted concept of secularism. As we all know, secularism connotes equal respect for all religions. But the BJP's actions flagrantly flout the very basic principles of secularism. It is a matter of deep concern that the politics of communalism and sectarianism is threatening to undermine India's long-cherished tradition of eclecticism and tolerance. The Hindu religion is misrepresented by the BJP. Hindu religious preachers have not advocated hatred towards other religions and the destruction of their places of worship. The Sangh Parivar has been venting its wrath on the Muslims for long; in recent times, it has also been directing its ire against the Christian community. Such acts violate the norms of any civilized society. The BJP is now seeking to replace the ideal of 'Unity in Diversity'--extolled by Rabindranath Tagore--by the false concept of Hindu nationalism. This move would surely tear the national fabric to pieces. If India has to survive as a national entity, we need to frontally combat sectarian politics. The old equations are rapidly changing and a new consensus is emerging as the political space gets more sharply divided. Now, political parties, be they national or regional, are

required to take decisions on major policies and issues in order to ensure political stability at the centre.

While the country is searching for an alternative path for nation building, it needs to look at the model of administration provided by the Left Front Governments in West Bengal, Kerala and Tripura. Despite limited constitutional powers and acts of glaring injustice by the predominant regimes at the centre, these governments have ensured a popular participation in the implementation of different schemes and programmes to alleviate the hardship of the common people and uplift the economic condition of the poor and the deprived section of society. We started with comprehensive tenancy reforms, which aimed at combining distributive justice with increased productivity. A decade ago, the late Rajiv Gandhi, the then Prime Minister of India, while addressing the Panchayati Raj Sammelan for the Eastern Zone, lauded our efforts in the rural sector.

There is no denying the fact that West Bengal has created a new record in the recovery and distribution of surplus land. We have now decentralized our administration through municipalities and Panchayats down to the village level. Today 50% of the State's annual outlay is sent through the three-tier Panchayati Raj system.

Administrative decentralization has facilitated the emergence of a new generation of leadership. It has also opened up political opportunities for women who have a 33 per cent reservation in the local government. This provision was later incorporated into the Central Panchayat Act. As an inevitable result of the qualitative transformation of the rural scenario, the purchasing power of the people of West Bengal, especially in the villages, has recorded a significant growth. This has created the requisite social base for a new spirit of industrialization based on a partnership of the public and private sectors, foreign and indigenous capital. The changes in the countryside have been made possible through massive movements of the people against vested interests. It is important to note that by supporting and encouraging healthy cultural movements, we have been able to uphold the democratic and secular tradition of India.

Indian industry and agriculture have many shortcomings owing to the wrong priorities in the planning process. Regional disparities have increased with some states remaining unpardonably underdeveloped though they have enough natural resources the regime of controls, licenses and of freight equalization has taken their toll on states in the eastern region. Bihar and Orissa are a case in point where in spite of an abundance of natural resources, there are abysmal levels of poverty and deprivation, including starvation. The small northeastern states have suffered neglect over the years. The system of controls and Delhi's clout in dispensing favors through licensing have been relaxed due to external and internal pressures. The old system has been replaced by the new economic program, which is a mix of liberalization from controls and integration of the Indian economy with global markets. The belief, however, that reforms advocated by the World Bank-IMF for structural adjustment would almost overnight unleash the Indian tiger and usher in prosperity, has not worked in reality. Recently, the World Bank President, Mr. James Wolfensohn observed that stabilization measures alone would not be effective in arresting the current global meltdown. He stressed the need of longer-term plans for strong institutions, greater equity and social justice in the interest of ensuring political stability without which, he felt, financial stability would remain a distant goal. Poverty reduction should be at the heart of the Bank's mission, he asserted. These views are in conformity with what we have been stating all these years. The IMF, Managing Director, Mr. Michael Camdessus, also admitted to mistakes and asked for introspection on the

fund's role in a new world-order with unpredictable capital flows and cautioned the world about the onrush of wide-spread recession.

The public sector, the joint sector and the private sector have a role to play in our economy. Since the state sector and the private sector will co-exist remedial steps should be taken to eliminate the ills of the afflicted public sector units by studying them on a case by case basis. Technological up gradation, modernization and other rehabilitation measures have to be applied to bring them back to health. The public sector units need to be run professionally and made accountable to the people. But, the way-out is not to weaken and close down important units. This disastrous course of action has to be reversed. The private sector, too, should shed its negative features and act with greater social commitment.

While India cannot isolate itself from the global trends, it is undeniable that in 1991, the country went in for liberalization without preparing itself. The failure to provide a safety net to take care of the poor and the vulnerable, including industrial labor, has since extracted a price from the people of India. The country's financial sector reforms which were meant to take advantage of the economic reform agenda have not worked. The financial markets are witnessing a downturn that has been compounded by the problems of the global economy. One of the symbols of India's financial stability--UTI's Unit '64 the Scheme has suffered erosion shaking the confidence of the middle class, in particular, in India's economic management. These are indications of some of the burgeoning problems that India will have to face as we enter the 21st century. The planned development of the country has to continue, but priorities have to be redefined based on our experiences. We need to reassess the prescriptive World Bank-IMF blueprint, which has not helped our economy. This is not the forum where one can propose a fresh master plan for our development. One would say that discussions and introspection are necessary to arrive at some consensus. In assessing the performance of the economy, the condition of the vast masses should be the criterion and not that of the tiny few at the top.

The present system in India will continue. But within that system if the negative facets are eliminated, much better results will follow. We need to welcome investment from abroad and bring technology from the advanced nations. At the same time, India's achievements in the last 50 years, especially in science and technology, cannot be dismissed. We have to create conditions to harness our own resources for productive purposes and to provide adequate opportunities to the country's brilliant scientists, technologists, engineers, doctors and skilled labor so that India can march forward. We should not lose faith in ourselves and must pursue the objective of self-reliance.

A unique feature of India's foreign policy has been its reliance on an underlying domestic political consensus. The Nehruvian foreign policy had its strength in the principles of non-alignment and peace, which formed its corner stone. But this tradition was disrupted by the nuclear explosions conducted by the present central government in May this year. While the invention of the atom bomb by the United States of America was a significant and dangerous feature of the 20th century, the use of the bomb by that country on Hiroshima and Nagasaki in Japan led to a harrowing tragedy. For a long time, we believed that Japan was the first and the last country to experience a nuclear holocaust. The revival of the nuclear arms race in the Indian sub-continent and the five super-power failure to chalk out a timetable for the elimination of atomic and hydrogen bombs make us afraid for the future. India did undertake a nuclear explosion in 1974, and soon earned the accolade from the peace-loving people all over the world by restraining himself from further tests and advocating the elimination of such weapons. India's stand of using atomic energy for

peaceful purposes also evoked wide acclaim. The current tests have triggered a widespread apprehension that they have been motivated not so much by threats to national security as by internal political compulsions of generating jingoism to bolster a dithering coalition regime. Pakistan also appears to have followed the same path on identical perceptions. These explosions would surely provoke an arms race that would be economically disastrous for both India and Pakistan. I would like to see the peoples of both countries jointly working for the common objective of preventing a nuclear war. It is the people who should have the last say.

As India enters the 21st century, dark clouds hover over her political and economic horizons. After 50 years of independence, we have created a society where only 10 to 15 per cent of the population has benefited. This itself in real terms is large and provides a huge market that attracts foreigners. But we have to cater to the need for the remaining 80 to 85 per cent of the masses who have been neglected. Though India has been bruised, battered and threatened over the last 50 years, she has, nevertheless, managed to protect the rich diversities that characterize a multi-ethnic, multi-lingual, multi-cultural and multi-religious society, unique in its own way. The newest threat is from a peculiar ideological perversion of attempting a homogenization of the Hindu society. This concept of the Sangh Parivar of a Hindu Rashtra is meant to demolish the democratic fabric of our society. We must be on our guard.

The situation, however, is not irretrievable. What is imperative is to cleanse our socio-political environment of polluting influences. Morality in public life has become a casualty and politicians are primarily responsible for this situation. The people's consciousness has to be raised in order to confront this trend. All responsible political parties should come forward to play a leading role to stop this rot. Payoffs and corruption scandals should not have any place in this system. Stern measures will have to be adopted to deal with the black-money operations, which have now assumed colossal proportions. Even within the existing socio-political milieu, significant changes can be brought about, if the necessary political will is there. Our policies must be so directed that India can achieve freedom from want and hunger. Conditions will have to be made conducive to channelize the fruits of modern science and technology for the benefit of the common man. Stress will have to be placed on pursuing a development strategy that encompasses growth with equity and social justice to meet the basic needs of our people, such as food, clothing, shelter, education, jobs and safe drinking water. It is a sad fact that India, standing on the brink of the new millennium, has a population, 40 per cent of whom live below the poverty line.

The award conferred on him is a belated recognition of the position taken by him to swim against the currents of mainstream economics and to focus on improving the quality of life and prioritizing distributive justice. Dr. Sen upholds the need for developing societies like India to direct far more resources to education, healthcare, poverty alleviation, programs for reduction of gender disparities and a cleaner environment. Amartya Sen rightly points out that economic take-off requires an educated, healthy and socially secure population. Without investments in human capital, investments in every other form of capital fail to yield optimal results. Human capital is the link with the future and so is central to growth and development, and also the very heart of the typical modern economy.

The country, with its history of 'Unity in Diversity', has been able to maintain its democratic apparatus, despite many challenges. What we now need is to mobilize the broad left, democratic and secular forces to expose the bankruptcy of the present regime in Delhi. With optimism, we also notice healthy

political developments in this context. The fact that the organizers have invited me to deliver this address, knowing very well that my views may not be in line with theirs, is encouraging.

As we turn our attention to the world-scene, it is evident that the catchwords of today's economic reorganization are liberalization and globalization. But globalization, as the Human Development Report of 1997, published by the UN, states, "is proceeding largely for the benefit of the dynamic and powerful countries. While in international commerce, it has increased the subordination of the developing to the developed world in the internal functioning of nation-states, globalization has led to shrinkage in state involvement in national life which has exposed the poor to sudden shocks especially in the third world countries".

The report further states: "Since the publication of last year's Human Development Report the recorded number of billionaires in the world has increased from 358 to 447, with the value of their combined assets now exceeding the combined incomes for the poorest 50% of the world's people, up from 45% from the year before. These are obscenities of excesses in a world where 160 million children are malnourished, 840 million people live without secure sources of water and 1.2 billion lack access to safe drinking water."

India approach the next century, the world will become more and more aware of the negative effects of globalization. However, in an increasingly multi-polar world, we shall have to ultimately adjust to the New World order of globalization and mutual interdependence of economies. The nation-states, particularly in the developing world, need more time for preparation so that local industries, commerce and the financial markets can meet the challenges in the face of unequal competition that has suddenly been thrust on them. Competition must be there, but among equals.

"Men make their own history, but they do not make it just as they please: they do not make it under circumstances chosen by themselves, but under circumstances directly encountered, given and transmitted from the past."

It is no use my taking a subjective view of our country's development. In the background of the reality and objective conditions prevailing in the 20th century, I have to view our entry into the next millennium. But, one would like to add that capitalism is not the ultimate system of human civilization. In the 21st century, we look forward to the emergence of a socialist, non-exploitative and humane society, the first stage of a communist society. The socialist society which we envisage will not only ensure changes in the economic and social spheres but also creates a new man and establish a higher civilization where love, sympathy and altruism for fellow human beings reign supreme.

India have to raise the people's consciousness to work for such a society, while endeavoring to complete the unfulfilled tasks. Let us hope for a world-situation where wars, big or small, will have no place, where disputes will be resolved through negotiations and where peaceful coexistence among nations will prevail (Basu, 1998).

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